

ATTRIBUTES OF LANDSCAPE COMPONENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF ARCHITECTURAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RESIDENTIAL SETTLEMENTS IN JOS METROPOLIS, PLATEAU STATE

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Abstract: Landscaping plays an essential role in the quality of our environment, economic wellbeing of the people, as well as their physical and psychological health. However, insufficient understanding and documentation of how landscape components, such as vegetation and hardscape elements, contribute to the architectural identity and urban aesthetics still exists. This study surveyed the attributes of landscape components within the context of architectural characterization used in enhancing residential settlements in Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State, North-Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. A multistage sampling technique was employed to select residents in the study area. The data collected for this study was obtained from both primary and secondary sources. A total of 188 questionnaires were distributed, and 150 were retrieved representing 79.78% used for final analysis. The retrieved questionnaire were analyzed and presented using descriptive statistics and weighted average index analysis. The study revealed that landscape components were available to residents and it have significant environmental impacts. The paper therefore recommends that long term plans of integrating landscape components from inception of design by relevant professionals in the built environment and policy makers be encouraged as this promotes outdoor environmental beautification.

1.0 Introduction

The treatment of residential environments significantly impacts the health, productivity,

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and recreation of urban dwellers, with landscaping around homes helping to reduce environmental pollution. Studies show that direct contact with nature, greening, and landscapes benefits inhabitants. Landscapes, consisting of vegetation, plants, soil, water bodies, and topography, are essential for improving and sustaining quality of life in cities, suburbs, or rural areas (Igwe et al., 2018; Orewere et al., 2020a). The quality of the physical environment, influenced by available facilities, policies, and security measures, affects human attitudes and daily activities (Bello, 2016; Igwe et al., 2018). Based on this, Sati et al. (2016) assert that the image and attractiveness of towns and cities strongly influence people's perceptions. Poorly managed urban green spaces can undermine a city's appearance and discourage positive impressions, affecting its livability and economic prospects. Hence, a mutual relationship between people and their physical environments exists. Agreeing with this assertion, Onuwa et al. (2021) averred that landscape architects must consider this when designing spaces, as the perception of landscapes is localized and reflects human interaction with natural and cultural heritage. Accordingly, landscapes that contribute to the health and well-being of individuals are categorized into soft and hard components (Emechebe et al., 2020). Soft landscape, collectively known as vegetation, refers to the living or natural materials used in landscaping.

Shrubs, bushes, trees, grass or ground cover, mulches, and flower gardens are major soft landscaping components (Emechebe et al., 2020). Hard landscape, on the other hand, refers to inanimate elements that relate with accessibility and modify natural surfaces into paved or structured forms such as lighting, garden benches, kerbs, stones, steps, ramps, walls, bricks, concrete, metal, bollards, tiles, walkways, asphalt, paving, planters, and sculptures (Orewere et al., 2020b). Décor, such as water features, statuary, tree hangers, pottery, and lighting, further enhances spaces, while supporting features include birdhouses, beehives, feeders, tree houses, and trellises (Emechebe et al., 2020; Afolami et al., 2021). Architectural composition involves human-made spaces where people live, work, and recreate, ranging from buildings to cities (Sati, 2015). He averred that green space (soft components) integrated with hard spaces creates more aesthetically pleasing and diverse urban environments. However, in Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria, preliminary survey reveals insufficient understanding and documentation of how landscape components, such as vegetation and hardscape elements, contribute to architectural identity and urban aesthetics. This gap in knowledge may result in suboptimal urban design, negatively impacting environmental quality, visual appeal, and overall livability.

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Building on this context, global scholarship has reinforced the crucial role of landscape components in shaping sustainable settlements. For instance, Beatley (2016) emphasized that biophilic urbanism integrating nature into cities directly contributes to resilience, social cohesion, and ecological health. Similarly, Jim (2017) found that residential greening projects in Asian cities improved thermal comfort, reduced urban heat island effects, and strengthened neighborhood identity. In the African context, Adegun (2018) highlighted the role of community-managed green infrastructure in South African townships, showing that local perceptions of soft and hard landscapes strongly affect long-term maintenance and acceptance. These perspectives, when juxtaposed with the Nigerian case (Emechebe et al., 2020; Onuwa et al., 2021), reveal a consistent global trend: landscapes are not merely aesthetic additions but essential infrastructural elements that foster environmental sustainability, human well-being, and urban identity. Yet, in Jos metropolis, limited scholarly focus has been placed on how these components articulate architectural characterization at the residential scale.

Within Nigeria, however, several researchers have explored related issues in different contexts. Ejeh et al. (2016), Sati (2015), Sati et al. (2016), and Uduma-Olugu et al. (2018) reveal considerable attention to the perception

of landscapes affected by human activities in the built environment. For instance, Sati et al. (2016) surveyed the perceptible attributes of urban green spaces in Jos metropolis. A sample of five green spaces was selected through stratified and simple random sampling, with data obtained via structured interviews from 365 respondents. The outcome revealed that the attributes of green spaces play a generative role in the synergy of built form aesthetics and perceived green space. The study recommended preemptive action plans, including a long-term vision for green spaces and a policy framework to integrate such spaces into urban design across Nigerian cities.

Emechebe et al. (2020) also assessed landscape components in hospital environments in Enugu State, Nigeria. Using interview schedules and structured questionnaires on hospital users, they found that 83% of patients valued greenery, 77.68% reported improved recovery linked to landscapes, and 88% experienced reduced stress and therapeutic benefits. The study concluded that hospital landscapes strongly improve patient health and recommended integrating well-planned landscapes into hospital design for user well-being.

Although these previous studies have enhanced our understanding of architectural character within built environments, preliminary study within the Jos South area still reveals shortcomings and suggests the need for targeted

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interventions. It is in this light that this study examines the attributes of landscape components in the architectural characterization of urban residential settlements in Jos South Local Government Area of Plateau State. The study addresses the following research questions: What landscape components are utilised within the study area? How do tenants perceive the landscape components used in enhancing the built environment? This study is considered important as it addresses a significant knowledge gap, providing insights that can improve the liveability and well-being of residents in the area.

2.0 Methodology

This section describes the methodology used in this study. It describes the study location, the study area and methods chosen for this study. Moreover, this part explains the method of data collection, population of the study, and sample size. As posited by Goyol, (2019) research is an intensive activity that is based on the work of others and generating new ideas to pursue new questions and answers.

2.1 Study Location: Jos Metropolis, Plateau State

Jos is the administrative capital of Plateau State, Jos Metropolis (Figure 2) lies within latitudes $9^{\circ}45'00''N$ to $09^{\circ}57'00''N$ and longitudes $8^{\circ}48'00''E$ to $8^{\circ}58'00''E$. Jos is the administrative capital of Plateau State, with a population of about 3,206,531 (National

Population Commission, 2006). This is attributed largely to the unprecedented flux due to rural-urban and urban-urban migration fueled by insecurity in the state and elsewhere in Nigeria in the last two decades (Rikko et al., 2022).

2.2 Study Area: Jos South Local Government Area

Jos South is a Local Government Area in Plateau State, Nigeria, is home to the Governor's office in Rayfield and hence serves as the state's de facto capital. It is located between latitudes $9^{\circ} 36' 41.5915'' N$ and $9^{\circ} 51' 14.2973'' N$ and longitudes $8^{\circ} 38' 24.4785'' E$ and $8^{\circ} 57' 14.0240'' E$ (Figure 1). It has its headquarters in Bukuru, some 15 km from Jos, the state capital, in the north-western portion of the state. Kuru, Gyel, Du and Vwang are the four districts of Jos South. It has a population of 306,716 people (NPC, 2006) and a total land area of around $1,037 \text{ km}^2$ (Gonap et al., 2019; Owolabi & Ogunro, 2022). It has a cool climatic condition due to its altitude. The coldest period is between November and February with an average mean daily temperature of 18°C , while it gets warm between March and April before the onset of rain. The rainy season, which is between the months of May and October, has its peak in August. The mean annual rainfall varies between 1347.5 and 1460 mm per annum. The major inhabitants of the area are the Beroms (Adzande et al., 2015).

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Figure 1: Location of Jos Metropolis in Plateau State, Nigeria

Source: Department of Geography and Planning, University of Jos, 2024.

2.3 Method of Data Collection

This study employed a descriptive survey research design as its methodology. The research instruments used include questionnaires, non-formal interviews and direct observation schedule. The primary data were direct observations of planted and installed landscape components in the urban residential settlements and questionnaires were

administered to tenants within study areas; non-formal interview was also conducted. According to Kumar, (2011) the strength of non-formal (unstructured) interviews is the almost complete freedom they provide in terms of content and structure. As the researcher, you have complete freedom in terms of the wording you use and the way you explain questions to your respondents. Furthermore, secondary data was accessed both manually and online, from relevant text and publications on the subject matter; which form the background of the study.

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2.4 Sampling Techniques

Using simple random sampling, Jos South LGA was selected by balloting from a list of all 17 LGAs in Plateau State. In stage one, 5 wards out of the 16 political wards in Jos South LGA were selected using simple random sampling by balloting. These were Bukuru, Du A, Kuru A, Zawan B, and Gyel B wards. Second stage involved the random selection of 4 communities in each of the 5 wards. Lastly, from the lists of residents a random selection of 10% from the sample frame of 1,880 respondents from each of the 5 wards were selected, which gave a total sample size of 188 residents. However, only 150 questionnaires were retrieved and used for the purpose of this study. The data collected from the respondents were subjected to both descriptive statistics and weighted average index (WAI) for objectives (i) and (ii) respectively.

Weighted Average Index (WAI)

To analyze the perception of residents toward landscape components, the Weighted Average Index (WAI) technique was employed. This method was considered appropriate because it systematically converts ordinal data from the Likert scale into quantitative measures that allow ranking of factors based on their relative importance.

To determine the weight of each scale, each item was calculated by multiplying the frequency of

each response pattern with its appropriate nominal value and dividing the sum with the number of respondent to the items. Responses for the components in objectives are rated by using a three-point scale with the scoring order 3, 2 and 1 as high, moderate and low. A weighted average index (WAI) analysis was then estimated as adopted from Onuwa, et al., (2021); using the mathematical formula:

$$\frac{\sum fiwi}{\sum fi} = WI \div \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where:

Σ=Summation;

F = frequency;

W = weight of each scale;

i = weight;

WI = weighted index

3.0 Discussion of Findings

The findings are presented in three sections. The first discusses the identified landscape components utilized within the study areas. The second section is devoted to perception of landscape components in enhancing the built environment.

3.1 The landscape components utilized within the residential area

The landscape components most observed are detailed in Table 1 in the study area. Trees (70%), Fences (64.7%), Drainages (54%), Flowers/Shrubs (50.7%), Lighting (49%), Pedestrian walkways (44.7%), Driveways (41%), Stones/Rocks (36.7%), Statues (19%) and Fountains/Pools (10%). (Plate i, ii, iii & iv). The

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findings from this section confirmed with the studies of (Bello 2016; Orewere, et al., 2019) who identified different landscape components

installed in the environment to improve user satisfaction.

Table 1: landscape components utilized in the residential area

Element	Frequency*	Percent (%)
Trees	105	70
Fence	97	64.7
Drainages	81	54
Flowers/Shrubs	76	50.7
Lighting	71	49
Pedestrian walkways	69	44.7
Driveways	61	41
Stones/Rocks	55	36.7
Statues	33	19
Fountains/Pools	15	10

Source: Field work, 2024.

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Plate i: Variety of trees that provide shade, rest and **Plate ii:** Shrubs that beautify the comfort during hot weather environment

Source: Field work, 2024.

Plate iii: Inter-locking stones to direct pedestrian movement

Source: Field work, 2024.

Plate iv: Cobbles used as the base for the focal point of a statue

3.2 Perception of landscape components in enhancing the built environment

Table 2 reveals the weighted index of landscape components in enhancing the built environment. The ranking of improvement in visual and aesthetic appeal of the built environment 2.97 (1st), conserves energy and facilitates biophysical interaction 2.61 (2nd) and promotes sustainable ecological management

2.35 (3rd) values are considered the most important landscape component in enhancing the built environment. Others include enhancing sustainable recreation and tourism potentials 2.26 (4th), social and mental integration between human and environment 2.14 (5th), and reduces maintenance cost of buildings 1.98 (6th) respectively.

Table 2: Perception of landscape components in enhancing the built environment

Item	Σfiwi	WI	Rank
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Improves visual and aesthetic appeal of the built environment	445	2.97	1
Conserves energy and facilitates biophysical interaction	391	2.61	2
Promotes sustainable ecological management	352	2.35	3
Enhances sustainable recreation and tourism potentials	339	2.26	4
Encourage social and mental integration between human and environment	321	2.14	5
Reduces maintenance cost of buildings	297	1.98	6

Note: The highest weighted index indicates the most important landscape component in enhancing the built environment.

Source: Field work, 2024.

This finding concurs with the study of Sati, et al., (2016) who affirmed that attributes of green spaces play the generative role in the process expressed by the synergy of the aesthetics of the built form with green space that is perceived. In addition, Orewere, et al., (2022a), affirmed that landscape development of outdoor environments enhances user satisfaction and improve productivity levels.

4.0 Discussion of Results

Results of this study revealed various landscape components utilized within the study areas. Trees, fences, drainages, flowers/shrubs, lighting, pedestrian walkways, driveways, stones/rocks, statues are some of the identified landscape components in the study area. Resident’s perception of these components

include visual and aesthetic appeal of the built environment, encourages social and mental integration between human and environment as well as enhancing sustainable ecological management amongst others. Generally, landscape components adds dimension and style to an environment, as well as transform characterless area to places of peace and pleasure for human comfort.

5.0 Conclusion

This study examined how soft and hard landscape components contribute to the architectural characterization of residential settlements in Jos South. Findings from the Weighted Average Index analysis show that residents strongly value features such as greenery, lighting, fences, and walkways, not only for their aesthetic appeal but also for improving security, accessibility, and social interaction.

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The study affirms that landscapes are essential infrastructural elements that enhance environmental quality, livability, and community identity. It recommends that architects and urban planners deliberately integrate both soft and hard landscape components into housing estates and city design to foster sustainability, social cohesion, and ecological resilience.

6.0 Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation provides an elaborate and systematic plan of action for enhancing existing conditions of landscape components of Jos metropolis:

1. Built environment professionals should prioritize the integration of both soft and hard landscape components into the design of private spaces. This will enhance the aesthetic appeal, functionality, and environmental quality of residential areas in Jos metropolis
2. There is the need for more awareness and sensitization of occupants, land owners and developers about the importance of landscape components not being destroyed or stolen but rather these elements add beautify to the environment.
3. Landscape design guidelines should be developed and incorporated into urban development policies to ensure that new projects contribute positively to the overall urban character.

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References

- Adzandeh, E.A., Akintunde, J.A., & Akintunde E.A. (2015). Analysis of Urban Growth Agents in Jos Metropolis, Nigeria. *International Journal of Remote Sensing and GIS*, 4(2) 41-50.
- Afolami, J. A., Kazeem, R. I., and Bobadoye, S. A. (2021). Assessment of Setback Requirements and Landscape Elements Availability at a Federal University Neighbourhood in Akure, Nigeria. In Agele, S.O and Oladeji, S.O. *Proceedings of the 4th Edition of World Environmental Conservation Conference: “Strengthening Sustainable Development Goals in Covid-19 Era”*, 5th June, 2021, pp.222-236.
- Bello, A.V. (2016). The effect of landscaping on rental values of residential property in Ijapo housing estate Akure, Nigeria.

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African Journal of Geo-Science Research,
4(1), 1-6

Ejeh, E. D.; Adedire, J. & Salihu, M. M. (2016).
The Influence of User Perception and
Social Sustainability on Architectural
Design. In Ebohon, O. J., Ayeni, D. A,
Egbu, C. O, and Omole, F. K. Procs. Of
the Joint International Conference (JIC)
on 21st Century Human Habitat: Issues,
Sustainability and Development, 21-24
March 2016, Akure, Nigeria, pp. 158-163

Emechebe, L.C., Eze, C.J., Lembi, J.J., &
Akande, O.K. (2020). Assessment of
Landscape Components in Hospital
Environment for General Hospital
Buildings in Enugu State, Nigeria.
International Journal of Landscape
Planning and Architecture, 6(2): 01–10.

Gonap, E. G., Ogoina, H.P., & Nalkap, T. (2019).
A Survey of Sports Tourism Facilities in
Jos. International Journal of Innovative
Research and Development, 8(7), 49 –
52. DOI No. :
10.24940/ijird/2019/v8/i7/JUL19007

Goyol, S. S. (2019). Building Agrarian
Infrastructure Resilience against Climate
Change Impacts: A Case of Plateau State
Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis,
School of the Built Environment
University of Salford, Submitted in

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Partial Fulfilment of the Requirement of
the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy. Pp.
118 – 124.

Igwe, P.U., Chinedu, O.C., Nlem, E.U., Nwezi,
C.C., & Ezekwu, J.C., P. (2018). A Review
of Landscape Design as a Means of
Controlling Gully Erosion. International
Journal of Environment, Agriculture and
Biotechnology (IJEAB) 3(1), 103-111.

National Population Commission (2006). 2006
Population and Housing Census of the
Federal Republic of Nigeria. Plateau
State Priority Tables Abuja, National
Population Commission: 1-2.

Onuwa, G.C., Joshua, V.I., Kambai, C.,
Terzulum, J.I. & Orewere, E. (2021).A
Technical report (paper) on the
Environmental Impacts of Landscape
Elements among Urban Residents.
Agriculture and Environment, 2(9):34-
39, Article ID: AEN-2021-02-09-012.

Orewere, E., & Ogenyi R. A. (2019). Soft
Landscaping and Its Impact in
Enhancing the Status of Nigerian Urban
Centres: A Case of Jos City Centre,
Nigeria. Journal of Environmental
Science and Resources Management.
11(2), 17-36.

Orewere, E., Katyen, A.M., & Tarni, M.A. (2020a). The Effect of Landscaping on Health and Environment in Housing Estate, Jos Nigeria. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 4(7): 16-35.

Sati, Y.C., Uji, Z. A., & Popoola, O. J. (2016). Perceptible Attributes of Urban Green spaces in the Architectural Characterization of Metropolitan Areas in Jos, Nigeria. *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(4), 71-77.

Orewere, E., Owonubi. A., Lapkat Luka Go'ar & Oguledo, C.A. (2020b). Enhancing Outdoor Landscape Development through the Use of Stones in Jos, Plateau State. *Journal of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences*. 9 (2), 32-43. DOI: 10.15640/jaes.v9n2a5

Owolabi, A., & Ogunro, T.O. (2022). Assessment of the Sustainability of Land covers Due to Artisanal Mining in Jos Area, Nigeria. *Research Square*, 1-33. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1587151/v1>

Perception - In Merriam-Webster's online dictionary (2014). (11th ed.). Retrieved from <http://www.merriamwebster.com/dictionary>

Rikko, L. S, Pwajok, N. R., Namu, J. A., & Habila, S. K. (2022). Depletion of Urban Green Spaces in Jos Metropolis, Nigeria. *Sahel Journal of Geography, Environment & Development*, 3(2), 67-77.

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